

MOSAIC

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy

Task 5.4

ERRIN
25/03/2021

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0. Executive Summary

The MOSAIC project requires the construction of a Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy to set out the actions that will be undertaken and the means for their realisation to build a consistent project identity and a common communication and dissemination approach among the project partners. This will enable the successful delivery of the MOSAIC project's communication and dissemination objectives and, subsequently, deliver impact to the project activities.

The document provides:

- A description of how each of the objectives of MOSAIC communications will be achieved
- An analysis of the target audiences of communications and dissemination actions
- An analysis of the different levels of dissemination actions
- A description of the communications architecture and a timeline of activities
- An analysis of the various communications tools that the project will use
- A description of the project' visual identity rules and the use of the European Commission logo
- The purpose of a set of guidelines for the project website
- Guidelines for the use of social media in MOSAIC

Deliverable Information

D5.1 – Title of the deliverable	
Deliverable number	D5.1
Responsible partner	ERRIN
Due date of deliverable	31/03/2021
Actual submission date	
Version	1
Authors	Hilary Webb, Heidi Johansson, Ryan Titley
Reviewers	
Work package number	5
Work package title	Mutual Learning, Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
Work package leader	ERRIN

Dissemination Level		
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>
PU	Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
PP	Restricted to other programme participants, including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium, including the Commission Services	<input type="checkbox"/>

Nature of the Deliverable		
R	Report	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
D	Demonstrator	<input type="checkbox"/>
W	Website, patent filing, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
O	Other	<input type="checkbox"/>

Partners Involved in the Deliverable

Participant No.	Name of the Organisation	Short Name	Involved
P5	European Regions Research and Innovation Network	ERRIN	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Long Form
EC	European Commission
CCP	Communication Contact Point
COP	Community of Practice
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
PCT	Project Communication Team
R&I	Research and Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SwafS	Science with and for Society

List of Terminology

Terminology	Definition/Explanation
Co-Creation	Co-creation is a form of collaborative innovation rooted in working together. The product of co-creation is created by multiple people from different backgrounds and disciplines. It can be applied in many different settings.
Community of Practice	The Community of Practice refers to all the mirror ecosystems within MOSAIC.
Horizon Europe Missions	EU missions are commitments to solve major societal challenges like fighting cancer, adapting to climate change, protecting our oceans, living in greener cities and ensuring soil health and food. They operate as a portfolio of actions with measurable goals.
Innovation ecosystem	An innovation ecosystem is an interconnected network of quadruple helix stakeholders, including academia, industry and different levels of the public

	sector and civil society. This multi-level approach applies a systemic and bottom-up approach to creating research, innovation and knowledge.
Mirror ecosystem	A mirror ecosystem is a replication site that will continue to test MOSAIC's methodology after the piloting phase. Collectively the mirror ecosystems form the Community of Practice.
Mission area: climate-neutral and smart cities	This Horizon Europe mission's aim is to support, promote and showcase 100 cities in their systemic transformation towards climate-neutrality by 2030.
Open innovation	Open innovation is an innovation mindset that encourages an out-of-silos approach. Collaboration extends beyond a single organisation and can include innovation practices such as innovation ecosystems.
Pilot ecosystems	This refers to the two pilots where MOSAIC's methodological approach and research actions will be tested throughout the project. The pilot ecosystems are Brussels and Milan.
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation is an approach anticipating and assessing potential implications and society expectations in regard to research and innovation. The approach aims to foster the design of inclusive and sustainable research and innovation.
SwafS	The Science with and for Society programme addresses European societal challenges tackled by Horizon 2020, building capacities and developing innovative ways of connecting science to society. It makes science more attractive, raises the appetite of society for innovation and opens up future research and innovation activities.

1. Introduction

This document presents deliverable 5.1, the Communications, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Strategy for the MOSAIC project. The purpose of this document is to provide a unified approach to all communication and dissemination activities within and around the project. This will enable all project partners to effectively communicate and actively contribute to the joint communication and dissemination objectives.

The purpose of the MOSAIC project's communication and dissemination activities is to disseminate project results, messages and activities, to build capacity for changing attitudes towards RRI, to raise awareness about RRI-based approaches to quadruple helix co-creation in mission-like settings, to influence decision-making, and to foster dialogue with and between existing Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) initiatives in regional development and in previous and ongoing Horizon 2020 (H2020) projects.

The CDE Strategy will constitute the core document that aims to identify dissemination boosters and outline the activities, tools and timing of the MOSAIC project's communication and dissemination activities. It also provides a thorough mapping and overview of the project's target groups, which will guide all the project's communication activities. The MOSAIC project is comprised of a diverse set of partners with varied expertise, reach and communication capabilities. Therefore, the strategy mobilises a range of different options to allow for a multi-platform approach to communication and dissemination and presents guidelines, recommendations, and best practices that aim to effectively guide and assist the project partners in their communication efforts. The strategy also focuses on the capitalisation of project partners existing networks, seeking out future opportunities for collaboration and partnerships.

A combination of traditional (e.g. presentations at events, promotional material and scientific publications) and digital dissemination tools (e.g. interactive webinars, urban storytelling techniques and blog posts) will be developed to exploit a diverse range of information channels and address broader target groups. The exploitation strategy within the CDE Strategy will focus on co-creation, mutual learning, and the conditions for replication by closely following the MOSAIC Community of Practice, making use of T5.1 and T5.2. The CDE Strategy will be updated twice during the lifetime of the project (M12 & M24) to consider developments in the project, the effectiveness of specific tools, and the changing nature of the target groups. The list and the description of significant events (conferences, seminars, workshops) organised by MOSAIC will also be detailed in the first release of the plan (M3).

ERRIN will further develop the MOSAIC project identity, based on the current logo, to include posters, flyers and templates for project documents and presentations (detailed description in Section 8 - Visual guidelines). ERRIN will create a project website (M3), which will present the project's mission, activities, developments and results in an accessible, user-friendly and visually appealing way. A local Communication Contact Point (CCP) will be appointed for the pilots, responsible for posting regular updates and visuals describing the experimentation, acting as an ambassador both within the ecosystem and the outside world. The website set-up, maintenance and implementation will be managed by ERRIN in cooperation with all other partners for content provision and population. Social media channels (Twitter and LinkedIn) will be used to raise awareness of the project's work and facilitate connectedness between peers.

1.1 Statement of purpose

The MOSAIC CDE Strategy illustrates how effective communication can be used to:

- Achieve the overall project goals
- Empower local and regional governments and their quadruple helix stakeholders
- Disseminate the MOSAIC outputs to identified target groups and key stakeholders
- Raise awareness of RRI-based approaches and models for quadruple helix co-creation and collaboration
- Create synergies with European policy frameworks
- Create opportunities for collaboration with other projects and initiatives

2. Our Voice

This section of the CDE strategy will set out the objectives and messaging around the MOSAIC project. This in turn, will ensure that all partners are coherently communicating about the project.

2.1. What are we talking about?

The project team must understand the concepts behind communication, dissemination, and exploitation to effectively implement this strategy.

2.1.1. Communication

“Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.”

(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)

Objective: Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g. by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.

Focus: Inform about and promote the project AND its results/success.

2.1.2. Dissemination

“The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.”

(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)

Objective: Transfer knowledge & results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of EU-funded research.

Focus: Describe and ensure results available for others to USE -> focus on results only!

2.1.3. Exploitation

“The utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.”

(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)

Objective: Effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society

Focus: Make concrete use of research results (not restricted to commercial use.)

Figure 1 - Venn diagram of CDE

2.2. Communication & Dissemination Objectives

Below are the five central dissemination objectives of the MOSAIC project:

1. Raise awareness by increasing the public visibility of key initiatives, shared visions, and calls for innovative solutions including the MOSAIC Community of Practice call. This information should be accessible by all, no matter how familiar they are with RRI.
2. Engage key stakeholders by motivating and mobilising them on a territorial and European level to encourage participation in the pilot activities and the replication initiatives.
3. Build a community through effective communication of MOSAIC's results and achievements across Europe to develop the replication activities but also to develop a larger community of interest around RRI-based approaches towards co-creation and mission-like setting. An example being the engagement of ERRIN's low-carbon cluster working groups.
4. Influence decision-makers through targeted communications to those who can lead quadruple helix and open innovation collaboration.
5. Boost sustainability by building networking opportunities with other relevant projects, events or initiatives.

This document will work towards these objectives by detailing five points vital to its implementation:

1. Mapping target audiences to identify which stakeholders will be the primary targets of MOSAIC's communications
2. Define key messages tailored to respective target groups
3. Methodologies and tools for the dissemination of the key messages
4. The frequency of MOSAIC's communications
5. The responsibilities of who will be responsible for which dissemination actions

2.3. How to Talk about MOSAIC

2.2.1 Our Project in a Sentence

The MOSAIC project is developing and testing a methodology for Open Innovation and RRI in the context of the Horizon Europe Cities Mission.

2.2.2. Our Project in a Paragraph

MOSAIC is a European project establishing a bottom-up RRI approach grounded in the Horizon Europe Mission on climate-neutral and smart cities. Over three years, MOSAIC will develop and test an Open Innovation methodology and SwafS knowledge base in two pilot innovation ecosystems: Brussels and Milan. A Community of Practice will be developed to test the methodology in a wider pool of mirror ecosystems.

2.2.3. The Scientific Approach

In a world where it is now more important than ever to find concrete solutions to compelling health and environmental challenges. At the core of MOSAIC's vision is the ambitious aim to study, prove and assess that these can be made possible and enhanced by a shift from triple to quadruple-helix models that values societal engagement. Thus, the overall aim of the MOSAIC project is to understand how the full role of citizens in Open Innovation can be accomplished. It will do so by analysing enabling factors, providing and testing a sound methodological approach, and measuring such processes' impact on innovation and the quadruple-helix actors of innovation ecosystems. Several scattered examples, mostly happening through bottom-up and spontaneous initiatives such as fab labs, makers spaces and alike, have fostered the creation of creative solutions by patients or the implementation of alternative consumption patterns in local neighbours but have often failed to achieve impacts on innovation policies. On the contrary, decision-makers have often failed to engage citizens further than collecting opinions through surveys or concentrating efforts on explaining the value of investments in research and innovation. We believe that one of the reasons for the widespread absence of more robust participatory processes in the innovation landscape is the lack of an appropriate methodological framework, made accessible, understandable and employable by all concerned stakeholders, as well as the scarce availability of ways to assess the effects and outcomes of such processes. The research carried out in the MOSAIC project will look to address these challenges, narrowing its focus by conducting its work in the context of the Horizon Europe Mission on climate-neutral and smart cities.

2.3. Ten Key Messages

These ten key messages have been prepared to support all partners, including and beyond the Project Communication Team, to communicate the ambitions of MOSAIC successfully. These messages can be used as a guide when preparing to introduce MOSAIC in a policy paper, academic paper, in a meeting or at a conference. The messages are:

1. Explore and implement a bottom-up RRI approach to developing Open Innovation and a SwafS knowledge base
2. Provide and test a methodology in place-based innovation ecosystems, Brussels and Milan, within the context of the Horizon Europe Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities
3. Engage all parts of the quadruple helix and integrate citizens into the innovation ecosystem
4. Deepen the involvement of society in R&I to fuel a transition to Open Innovation throughout Europe
5. Set up a mutual learning process with cities involved in the Horizon Europe Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities, using a community of practice to inspire, connect and build capacity

6. Understand the changing relationship between science and society
7. Follow this long-term process by observing transformative changes happening within the innovation ecosystem as well as in individual stakeholders
8. Understand the role of citizens in Open Innovation
9. Acknowledge co-creation as an enabling factor of Open Innovation
10. Maximise the impact of investments by setting clearer targets and expected impacts when addressing global challenges.

As the project develops and evolves, these messages may be updated with the support of the Project Communication Team.

3. Target audience analysis

The MOSAIC project partners (and pilots) will perform a comprehensive stakeholder and target audience analysis designed to identify and map the stakeholders' groups relevant to the MOSAIC project. These identified stakeholder groups should be the target audience of the project's communication and dissemination activities, as they either have a potential interest in the project or a potential influence over the project's activities and outcomes. The identified stakeholder groups will be targeted at the different dissemination levels - local, regional, national, European and international – whenever relevant and applicable. Some stakeholder groups will be targeted at all dissemination levels, whereas others only will be targeted at one or a few of these levels. A detailed overview of how the different stakeholder target groups can be approached on the different dissemination levels is presented below in Table 2: Stakeholder and dissemination level matrix.

This analysis identifies five overarching categories of stakeholders, which are further sub-categorised into smaller groups. The key five overarching stakeholders include:

- Citizens
- Private sector
- Policymakers
- Scientific and research community
- Media

Figure 2 - Stakeholder Mapping

Table 1. Stakeholder Narratives breaks down the five overarching stakeholder categories into more specific sub-categories and sets out how MOSAIC's communication approach should be tailored to the intended audiences to ensure that each of the identified stakeholder groups are reached. More specifically, this table associates each group of stakeholders with a set of key narratives that should substantiate MOSAIC communication activities. It then provides an overview of the appropriate communication channels for conveying these messages through storytelling.

The narratives are, at this stage, indicative and designed to provide the reader with an idea of the types of content that should be promoted by project partners towards the different stakeholder group.

Table 1. Stakeholder Narratives

Stakeholders	Communication Aims – why are we targeting them?	Key Narratives and Outputs	Suggested Communication Channels	Key Moments for Communications Activity
<p>Citizens</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Citizens at the European, national and sub-national level ● Citizens from all socio-economic backgrounds and genders, with a focus on citizens from low- and moderate-income communities ● Civil Society Organisations and actors ● Citizens in the MOSAIC pilots – Brussels and Milan ● Citizens in the cities / metropolitan areas included in the Community of Practice 	<p>One of MOSAIC's central objectives is to empower diverse stakeholders, including citizens, to engage in innovation processes.</p> <p>The two MOSAIC pilots aim to involve a diverse range of citizens in the participatory processes which will take place in the cities.</p> <p>The MOSAIC project will gather experiences from the innovation ecosystems in the Community of Practice and engage them in the project's peer learning programme.</p>	<p>Narratives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Highlight and explain the importance of citizens' engagement and participation in the local innovation ecosystem and in innovation processes. ● Explain and emphasise the importance of the Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities, and what the Mission will mean for citizens. ● Encourage citizens to participate in the project's activities, especially in the pilot and replication activities. <p>Social media narratives should bear in mind the diversity of citizen groups and adapt the technical language accordingly.</p> <p>Outputs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Webpage and factsheets with summaries of pilot experiences ● MOSAIC Toolkit for the impact assessment of Open Innovation 	<p>Social media</p> <p>Direct contact with city authorities and Civil Society Organisations (CSOs)</p> <p>Local media</p>	<p>M1-M36: Highlight the importance of citizens' participation in innovation processes.</p> <p>M1-M36: Explain and highlight the importance of the Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities.</p> <p>M1-M30: Engage citizens in the quadruple-helix participatory processes in the two pilots – Brussels and Milan.</p> <p>M6-M36: Engage with citizens and encourage their active participation in the Community of Practice.</p> <p>M10-36: Share best practices and experiences from the pilot cities of how citizens' have contributed to the processes and results.</p>

<p>Private sector</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SMEs at the sub-national level • Local social innovators and entrepreneurs • Cluster organisations and representatives of industry associations at sub-national, national and EU level • Broader EU innovation community 	<p>The private sector has generally had a low involvement in RRI-supporting initiatives, which the MOSAIC project aims to address.</p> <p>Private sector representatives will be part of and engaged in the pilot experimentations and knowledge transfer activities to spread the culture of RRI, co-creation and mission-like project development on the ground.</p>	<p>Narratives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlight the importance of the participation of the private sector in open innovation processes. • Emphasise the importance of the Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities and the opportunities the implementation of the mission can bring for the private sector. • Encourage the private sector actors to participate in the pilot and replication activities. • Encourage the private sector actors to take part of the MOSAIC outputs, such as the Springer brief and the Cookbook, and to make use of the material in their activities and disseminate them further. <p>Outputs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brochure on 'co-creation initiatives for achieving climate-neutral cities' • Guidelines/factsheets on how to approach co-creation in mission-like projects • MOSAIC Cookbook 	<p>Invitations to pilot experimentation activities</p> <p>Invitations to the peer-learning programme activities</p> <p>Social Media</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Local media</p>	<p>M1-M36: Highlight the importance of the participation of the private sector in innovation processes.</p> <p>M1-M30: Engage private sector actors in the quadruple-helix participatory processes in the two pilots – Brussels and Milan.</p> <p>M15-M36: Private sector stakeholders should be actively approached to take part in peer-learning programme activities.</p> <p>M30-M36: Dissemination of the MOSAIC Cookbook and the guidelines/factsheets on how to approach co-creation in mission-like projects</p>
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<p>Policymakers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City governments in Milan and Brussels • National governments in Belgium and Italy • Cities and regions in Belgium and Italy • Cities, regions and the national governments of the cities involved in the Community of Practice • City and regional networks, e.g. Eurocities, ERRIN and POLIS, to reach local and regional policy makers across Europe • EU policy makers 	<p>City governments in the pilots and the Community of Practice will ensure the institutional dissemination of MOSAIC's activities, both internally and to national governments, as well as to other cities and regions through collaborative networks and organisations.</p> <p>The participation of the local policymakers will be crucial for the quadruple-helix co-creation activities in the pilot cities and in the knowledge transfer activities in the peer learning programme.</p>	<p>Narratives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlight MOSAIC's policy recommendations and guidelines and why they should be taken up. • Share know-how and insights on how to approach co-creation in mission-like projects. • Spread up-to-date information and developments related to the Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities. • Share stories and best practices from the pilot cities' activities as well as the experiences from the cities in the Community of Practice. <p>The project should develop targeted communications with a policy-focussed language.</p> <p>Outputs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MOSAIC Toolkit for the impact assessment of Open Innovation • Guidelines/factsheets on how to approach co-creation in mission-like projects • Recommendations for incentivising and fairly rewarding citizen participation in Open Innovation • MOSAIC Cookbook 	<p>Public documents including policy papers</p> <p>Meetings, webinars and high-level events</p> <p>Direct out-reach including emails</p> <p>Local media</p> <p>Newsletter</p>	<p>M1-M30: Engage policymakers in the quadruple-helix participatory processes in the two pilots – Brussels and Milan.</p> <p>M6-M36: Share the stories of the MOSAIC mirror ecosystems</p> <p>M10-36: Share best practices and experiences from the pilot cities which can inspire and teach policymakers in other cities how to adopt similar approaches.</p> <p>M15-M36: Encourage policymakers to play an active role in the peer-learning programme activities.</p> <p>M18-M36: Disseminate and raise awareness of the MOSAIC recommendations for incentivising and rewarding citizen participation in open innovation</p> <p>M30-M36: Dissemination of the MOSAIC Cookbook and the guidelines/factsheets on how to approach co-creation in mission-like projects</p>
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<p>Scientific and research community</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● PhD students and researchers ● National Research Councils ● The European Research Council ● Marie Skłodowska researchers and projects ● European university networks and associations 	<p>Scientific and research communities on the sub-national, national and European levels will be engaged to raise awareness of RRI and introduce formats they can use in their own work.</p> <p>The scientific community will be mobilised and engaged as part of the co-creation activities taking place in the MOSAIC pilots and in the mirror ecosystems.</p>	<p>Narratives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Share the MOSAIC project's scientific outputs, articles and results. ● Invite the scientific community to disseminate further and make use of the project's outcomes in their own work. ● Encourage the scientific community to take part in the project's quadruple-helix co-creation activities in the pilots and in the replication activities. <p>Outputs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Handout on 'SwafS 2014-2020: exploiting co-creation in R&I' ● MOSAIC Toolkit for the impact assessment of Open Innovation ● Springer Brief on co-creation in action in open innovation ● MOSAIC Cookbook 	<p>Newsletter</p> <p>Engagement through local ecosystems</p> <p>Website</p> <p>Social media</p> <p>Academic events</p> <p>Scientific publications</p>	<p>M1-M30: Engage the scientific community in the quadruple-helix participatory processes in the two pilots – Brussels and Milan.</p> <p>M11-M36: Share MOSAIC's scientific outcomes, such as the Springer Brief and the Toolkit, with the scientific community and encourage them to make use of the results in their own work.</p> <p>M15-M36: The scientific community should be approached to take part in the peer-learning programme activities.</p>
<p>Media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Local and regional media ● TV ● Radio ● Print media ● Online media 	<p>Media actors should be engaged to ensure the wider communication of the MOSAIC project and its results and activities.</p> <p>Local and regional media provides a way to reach citizens and private sector actors and inform them about the project activities,</p>	<p>Narratives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Share MOSAIC key activities, results and milestones with local media, such as TV, print and online media, and radio. ● Create stories around the key outcomes and highlight why these are important for the city in question. 	<p>Events</p> <p>Direct out-reach including emails</p> <p>Website articles</p>	<p>M1-M30: Local media could be important for reaching all quadruple-helix stakeholders needed for the participatory processes in the two pilots – Brussels and Milan.</p> <p>M10-36: Share stories from the pilot cities and the mirror ecosystems, which can inspire</p>

	<p>especially in the pilots and mirror ecosystems.</p>	<p>Project actors should capitalise on existing contacts with local journalists to foster media coverage of the project's activities especially for large project events such as the final conference.</p> <p>Outputs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Webpage and factsheets with summaries of pilot experiences • MOSAIC Mirror ecosystems digital stories 		<p>other cities to adopt similar approaches.</p> <p>M15-M36: Local media could be important for reaching quadruple-helix stakeholders and encourage them to participate in the peer-learning programme activities.</p>
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3.2. Working Together

MOSAIC will look to foster a dialogue with other projects (past and ongoing) and initiatives addressing challenges related to RRI and the Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities. The purpose of this is to support the dissemination efforts and contribute to the multiplier effect by reaching out to projects and networks that share similar interests and compatibilities with the project. Targeting these actors will boost the dissemination reach of the project results and help shape MOSAIC communication actions by avoiding an overlap of activities and coordinating complimentary work processes.

Other actors will be targeted through:

- Joint meetings with other networks to inform on latest developments and discuss potential opportunities for collaboration
- Regularly share information on relevant topics and find/create opportunities for collaboration
- Participation in events and activities organised by other networks and projects to support their projects and results and to promote MOSAIC
- Mutual engagement on social media.

Projects already identified:

Figure 3 - Connecting the Dots

3.3. Connecting the Dots:

The above projects have been followed on Twitter by the MOSAIC account in order to engage the shared networks of the ongoing and past projects. MOSAIC will also use its partners' networks to develop collaborative activities with the identified projects and their partners. For example, ERRIN can engage ENOLL, a partner in SISCODE, through ERRIN and ENOLL's mutual involvement in the [UNaLab](#) project.

MOSAIC will aim to organise the first joint meeting with other RRI projects and networks within the first year of the project.

3.4. Dissemination levels

The MOSAIC project consortium has made extensive efforts to design its communication approach to ensure that the right message is delivered to the appropriate target audience. This approach requires consideration on how communication activities should be adapted to the dissemination levels - local, regional, national, European or international - and which communication channels should be used to reach the different levels. Material disseminated at several levels must be calibrated to effectively show the overall benefits of the MOSAIC project's activities and work.

Within the project consortium, some partners are better positioned to communicate at certain levels of dissemination, identified above. The project results should be primarily disseminated by those who have been involved in their development, but MOSAIC will also utilise the capacities of other partners. An analysis of the anticipated capacities is below.

- **Local:** The MOSAIC pilot cities and the cities involved in the Community of Practice are best placed on disseminating information to their local stakeholders. They will have a greater understanding of the local media landscape and communication channels and can nuance their messaging to ensure that it aligns with the local context. Materials can also be produced in local languages.
- **Regional:** The regional networks that are participating in the project, such as ERRIN and SoScience, are best placed on disseminating at a regional level, as they already have the communications infrastructure to disseminate information to their members in place and can utilise the communication capacity of the regional offices they work with. City authorities will also have a similar potential.

Mobilising the membership of networks like ERRIN's will allow materials to be distributed to relevant regional stakeholders that can then be passed on to local stakeholders, creating a virtuous multiplier effect. Similarly, external engagement can lead to a 'trickle-down effect' with dissemination products making their way to regional or national organisations.

- **National:** National dissemination is best achieved through partners with a strong presence in multiple locations in one member state, such as universities. These partners can use their internal networks and contacts with other actors and organisations to disseminate information to different parts of the country. Similarly, they will host and attend events and share materials that cater to a specific national audience.
- **European:** Participation in European networks is the most effective way to communicate information to stakeholders across Europe. Organisations like ERRIN have an international membership spread across Europe and are thus well placed to achieve pan-European reach for their communications. They also have the capacity to produce content in a range of different languages. Similarly, high-level policymakers can be targeted as these networks host numerous events and policy sessions online and in Brussels and have staff dedicated to policy advocacy. Additionally, ERRIN has been following the development of the Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities closely and has contributed to the Mission Board and the European Commission's work. ERRIN will therefore provide a natural link for the MOSAIC project to the policy developments related to the Mission.
- **International:** Partners with global networks/partnerships or physical presences external to the EU are best placed on disseminating internationally: they can utilise their existing networks and introduce new international audiences to MOSAIC's work. Incorporating these actors into the project's central communications will increase the likelihood of engagement with the project and further exploit the results and replication on a larger scale.

Table 2: Stakeholder and dissemination level matrix

An overview of the communications capabilities of the individual consortium partners can be found in Annex Error! Reference source not found..

	Citizens	Private sector	Policymakers	Scientific and research community	Media
Local	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local media and communication channels Events and meetings Targeted communication material, e.g. flyers Social media CSOs and other local actors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local media Events and meetings Social media Newsletter Direct out-reach, e.g. emails 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local media Events and meetings Direct out-reach, e.g. emails Newsletter Policy papers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local media Events and meetings Scientific publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct out-reach, e.g. emails Events
Regional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local and regional media Events Social media CSOs and other regional actors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local and regional media Events Social media Newsletter Direct out-reach, e.g. emails 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local and regional media Events and meetings Direct out-reach, e.g. emails Newsletter Policy papers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local and regional media Events and meetings Scientific publications Newsletter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Direct out-reach, e.g. emails Events
National	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Media Social media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Media Social media Newsletter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy papers Media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academic events Social media Newsletter Scientific publications Media 	
European	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media Website 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy papers Social media Newsletter Events Networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academic events Newsletter Social media Scientific publications 	
International				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific publications Academic events 	

4. Communication Architecture

MOSAIC is a project incorporating a range of different stakeholders with a range of additional communications requirements. Therefore, it is essential to set out an overview of how communication activities will be organised and structured.

4.1. Responsibility

ERRIN is the organisation with overall responsibility for the dissemination and communication activities and so will be at the forefront of managing and coordinating communication activities. However, one person from each consortium partner will be responsible for communications; together, they will form the Project Communication Team (PCT). Moreover, there will be a Communication Contact Point (CCP) in each of the pilot cities.

The Project Communication Team (PCT) will ensure that all consortium members:

1. Use their own communications channels to amplify MOSAIC communication activities by disseminating MOSAIC communications produced by ERRIN
2. Provide the subject matter expertise to ensure the MOSAIC project's central communications are rigorous, substantive, and support the exploitation of results by external organisations and ensure the replication and upscaling of project results.

The Communication Contact Point (CCP) in each of the pilot cities will be responsible for:

1. Providing written and visual updates describing the experimentation
2. Acting as an ambassador for MOSAIC within its ecosystem and outwardly
3. Liaising with local press contacts using resources supplied by ERRIN.

Figure 4: Information flow

4.2. Proposed Workflow

The below workflow presents an overview of the steps that should be taken in order to communicate MOSAIC's activities effectively.

Figure 5 - Proposed Communication Workflow

4.2.1. Content generation

An overview document on content generation for MOSAIC's communication channels will be made available to all partners. This will facilitate the collaboration between ERRIN as the work package leader, the PCT and the CCPs in the pilot and mirror ecosystems. The document will be a yearly overview plan indicating what content is expected to be published or shared in which month, and which partner is responsible for creating the content. See Figure 6 - Content generation overview calendar sample.

	MOSAIC content generation calendar 2021				
	April	May	June	July	August
Website					
Blogs	Brussels	Milan			
Videos					
Interviews					
Events					
Policy papers					
Academic articles					
News				Mission on climate neutral and smart cities expected to enter implementation phase - ERRIN	
Social Media					
Twitter	Story telling campaign: Brussels - via CCP	Story telling campaign: Milan - via CCP			
LinkedIn					
Newsletter			Newsletter 1		
Promotional material					

Figure 6 - Content generation overview calendar sample – information just as demonstration

Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101006382 - H2020-SwafS-2018-2020 / H2020-SwafS-2020-1

4.2.2. Timeline for Key Communications Activity

Effective communication activities are going to be essential to delivering the MOSAIC project. However, for the communications to be considered effective, strategic milestones for the project will need to be properly publicised. Below in Figure 7, you can find a timeline that sets out the communication activities that will be required in accordance with specific milestones.

Figure 7 - Timeline of Activities

5. Communications Channels and Tools

This section of the communications strategy sets out best practice tips and examples that can be used to boost the reach and impact of MOSAIC communications activities. Particular focus has been given to selecting the best social media channel to convey the appropriate project narrative. It will also introduce the main tools that will be used for communicating information regarding the project and the guidelines for using them within MOSAIC.

When choosing the correct channel, there are several questions to be considered:

5.1. What, Who, Why, When and How?

WHAT is the message?

The composition of the content interacts with the best way to share a message. Content that is text-heavy is best suited to the website, while solely visual content will have a greater impact on social media. Is there a call to action or key information that needs to be communicated? Are there statistics that should be highlighted?

WHO is the information for?

Different target audiences will respond to different mediums and channels: young people through social media, the press through emails, partners and other stakeholders through the website and newsletters. Understanding audience preferences can improve the impact of communications.

WHY am I sharing this?

The motive for posting is important - a post intended to engage directly with recipients is more suited to social media, whereas the website is better for sharing important information that needs to be stored permanently. Promoting MOSAIC is best done through professional channels.

WHEN should this be shared?

The lifespan of a tweet in 2021 is between 15 and 20 minutes, while a LinkedIn post is around 48 hours. Posts on both networks perform best at specific times of day and days of the week, detailed in the best practices below. The frequency and regularity of shared content are also important to maximise the impact of each tool.

HOW should I share this?

Each tool has restrictions and limitations. For example, Twitter has a 240 character limit while longer-form articles are much better suited to the website where the information will be retrievable. However, the same is not true for visual content. All these things must be considered in the MOSAIC communication activities.

5.2. Overview of channels and tools

Promotional Material: A variety of promotional material will be created to help publicise the project: brochures, presentations, a video, infographics and one pagers. These will cover a variety of topics, from reasons to collaborate with MOSAIC to the importance of co-creation in the mission approach. These can be created by ERRIN or by the PTO. Once created, they can be shared as needed, stored on the website and regularly shared via social media. Materials can also be created specifically for certain events to help promotion. They can then be repurposed for similar events in the future. All promotional material will feature the MOSAIC branding and visual style. Templates will be available so that partners can create documents independently. Until physical events resume after the COVID-19 pandemic, most of this material will be produced in a digital capacity. See examples of the leaflet and roll-up banner below:

Figure 8 Sample MOSAIC leaflet

Figure 9 Sample MOSAIC roll-up banner

Website: The MOSAIC website will be the public hub of all information related to the MOSAIC project, it will be MOSAIC's main repository and communication channel, hosting many of the tools listed below. The website will include a place for public project deliverables and outcomes; academic and policy papers; a calendar for project and related events; a news section featuring project and pilot updates as well as general news around RRI; co-creation and the cities mission and communication material from the project including infographics, leaflets and videos. There will also be a repository of all exploitable deliverables such as training materials like the MOSAIC Toolbox and the MOSAIC Cookbook. The website will host the pilot and mirror ecosystems profiles, where blog-style posts will document the mapping, experimentation and mutual learning activities taking place on the ground. This will bring about urban storytelling, with experiences being shared from the bottom-up via the pilot and mirror ecosystems. These will be based on the input of CCPs. The website will later support activities related to mutual learning for the Community of Practice with a flexible space featuring webinar links, interviews and forum discussions.

Policy Papers: Policy-related results and recommendations will be extracted from the project outputs and condensed into a series of policy papers that are aimed specifically at policymakers. The purpose of these documents will be to convince decision-makers to incorporate co-creation approaches into their future decision processes, and ultimately, contribute to climate neutral cities.

Given the different levels of decision-makers that the project will engage, partners are encouraged to adapt the documents in order to target the audience that they are most likely to be interacting with. For example, a document aimed at a Member of the European Parliament will make many of the same points as a document aimed at a member of the Brussels Capital Region, but with slightly different emphasis and examples. Policy papers will also feature the MOSAIC branding and visual styling.

Press Releases: Press releases will be released in two means: Top-down and bottom-up. Top-down press releases will be created when major project news, such as the launch, policy recommendations or substantial project results, are to be communicated to a wider audience, a press release will be prepared and shared with major European news organisations such as EurActiv, Politico, Policy Review, Reuters and other pan-European news agencies. Depending on the relevance, partners will also share with their own regional, national or even local media contacts. Bottom-up press releases will begin at a smaller level – either local or regional, and then be shared upwards to a national, or even pan-European level. Such press releases are for publicising events, project results in localities and other specific pieces of information that would not have relevance for a wider international audience. The CCP will be responsible for sharing these with the relevant local press contacts. All press releases will feature on the website as news items.

Scientific Publications: In order to disseminate research findings with the long-term impact of MOSAIC and the City Mission/Co-Creation in mind, the project will also target key relevant scientific journals. This list is not exhaustive, but rather means to convey the broad range of specialised journals that can be considered for the project and its thematic focus. Publication in these journals will lend legitimacy to the project results, whilst also encouraging external stakeholders to engage in the City Mission/Co-Creation activities. To this end, all publications will be open access to ensure ease of accessibility.

Newsletters and Emails: One of the primary means of stakeholder outreach in MOSAIC will be via e-mail to inform interested parties about events and activities. We will also use email to distribute a newsletter to all stakeholders that draws attention to MOSAIC highlights. Emails will allow for partners to conduct small scale, targeted outreach with a more personal feel, that is as flexible as possible and requires no coordination centrally; however, while e-mail is a simple form of communication, it can be difficult to strategically plan and measure its effectiveness.

MOSAIC will produce six newsletters, targeting a broader audience with information on MOSAIC research and insights for adaptation in Europe. The newsletter will be sent out via email through the web-based platform Mail Chimp, linking directly to website content. The use of an e-mail newsletter

allows for more detailed monitoring and evaluation data gathering. The newsletters will also be available in a public archive on the MOSAIC website. They will be sent to the database of contacts that the project establishes and, if possible, to contacts of the partners that are external to the project. The mailing list will be managed in line with GDPR guidelines via MailChimp, which will not sell the collected data under any circumstances¹.

Social Media: The project will be active on two social media channels: Twitter and LinkedIn. The Twitter account will share all project outputs, attempt low level interactions with persons of interest to the project, and interact with the other social media accounts of project partners and other projects dealing with co-creation and RRI. On LinkedIn, a public page and will be used to create a community around the concept of missions and co-creation and MOSAIC. The page will share project outputs and engage with stakeholders and policymakers less familiar with MOSAIC. The project will also consider using a group, either a pre-existing one or creating a MOSAIC-specific to catalyse discussions and connect experts.

Events: MOSAIC will be presented at events and will also organise events of its own to disseminate the project. For external events, a range of materials can be made available to help promote the project. Alongside giving MOSAIC a presence at these events, they provide an excellent opportunity to share the project with different audiences and organisations that could participate in the project. Until physical events can resume following the COVID-19 pandemic, it is expected that most events will take place virtually using platforms including Zoom, GoToWebinar and Microsoft Teams.

Image bank: A bank of images has been developed and will be added to the shared Next Cloud for all project partners to access. In order to keep MOSAIC's visual identity uniform and recognisable, partners should use these images when needed. They include: infographics, partner logos and portraits, stock-images related to co-creation and the pilot ecosystems, gifs, partner images and more. The bank will grow and develop as the project continues, eventually including pictures from the pilot and mirror ecosystems. Where partner images are used, the copyright or credit will be duly indicated.

¹ https://mailchimp.com/legal/privacy/?_ga=2.56467819.1560649861.1613645298-653844580.1596709448

5.3. Website

The project website constitutes an essential communication tool to increase the project visibility and impact, especially towards wider communities and the general public. Online and regularly updated, the MOSAIC website will contain all relevant information about the project, including

- project objectives;
- news;
- events;
- academic papers;
- policy papers;
- partner information;
- pilot and mirror city profiles;
- exploitable deliverables
- training material.

The website content will not be limited to project activities and results but will also include other helpful information related to the Cities Mission, RRI and Co-Creation.

5.3.1. Homepage

The homepage will be the landing page for most visitors to the website. It will briefly introduce the project and easily direct users to the specific content they are searching for or give them a chance to learn more about the project and recent related news.

5.3.2. About

This section will introduce the project in detail and comprise of subsections with more information about:

- MOSAIC
- Project partners and the team working on MOSAIC
- Pilot regions
- Mirror regions and the Community of Practice

Due to coronavirus restrictions, it is not possible to take unified pictures of the MOSAIC team, and so partners will be requested to provide images meeting the following specifications:

- Portrait photo, ideal aspect ratio 1:7 – not landscape
- Taken in daylight, ideally with a plain or straightforward background behind you
- Headshot – shoulders and above
- No filters – unedited photos, i.e. not in black and white.

Generated avatars may be introduced to unify the team's visual identity, depending on the quality of the images provided.

5.3.3. Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities

This section will introduce the Horizon Europe cities mission as the context of the MOSAIC project. Visitors will learn more about the mission and missions in general, but this section will also serve as a repository of the latest news and events related to the mission.

5.3.4. What is Co-Creation

This section will showcase the concept of co-creation as a tool both within and outside of the MOSAIC project.

5.3.5. Events

This calendar function will direct visitors to upcoming and past events, displayed in chronological order. For MOSAIC events, event pages will host registration.

5.3.6. News

This section will gather the latest news from the MOSAIC project and the relevant subjects surrounding the project, including missions, specifically the city mission, RRI and co-creation. Published issues of the MOSAIC newsletter will also be available here.

5.3.7. Resources

Resources such as policy or academic papers, exploitable deliverables and project materials will be available to view and download.

5.4. Website Monitoring

As stipulated in the project application, the MOSAIC website has several key performance indicators (KPIs) to reach:

KPI	M18	M36
SEO insights for Google Organic	1000	5000
Links for contents	100	500
Mobile Performance Analysis	20%	40%
Total number of downloads of MOSAIC deliverables	70	200

To ensure these KPIs are reached on time and to be able to monitor the success of the MOSAIC website, Google Analytics will be used to monitor:

- Users (total and new)
- Sessions
- Pageviews
- Acquisition
- Social referrals
- SEO insights
- Link clicks
- Downloads

Key statistics will be gathered monthly by ERRIN and added to an Excel sheet, which will be monitored closely in order to detect any negative or positive trends as well as user patterns for the MOSAIC website. This will enable ERRIN and the PCT to correct and update the project's communication efforts linked to the website if necessary.

Figure 10 Top tips for generating website traffic

6. Social media

MOSAIC will use social media to communicate its progress and outcomes and learn about and engage with other initiatives related to RRI, co-creation, and the Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities. The project will use Twitter and LinkedIn. Different social media channels should be used in different ways. A tweet's lifespan in 2021 is between 15 and 20 minutes, while a LinkedIn post is around 48 hours².

Figure 11 - Average Lifespan of a Social Media Post

The following guidelines should support partners and communications officers as they share MOSAIC on social media. While the project will officially only use LinkedIn and Twitter, project partners may choose to share MOSAIC content on their pages on other channels such as Facebook and Instagram. The below table, Figure 12 - Social Media Profiles, offers an overview of all the MOSAIC and partners' social media pages so that partners can be tagged where possible to increase dissemination impact.

² <https://id.oberlo.com/blog/best-time-post-social-media>

Figure 12 - Social Media Profiles

Partner	LinkedIn	Twitter handle	Twitter Link	Facebook	Instagram	Website
MOSAIC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/mosaic-eu	MOSAIC_EU	https://twitter.com/MOSAIC_EU	N/A	N/A	http://mosaic-mission.eu/
ERRIN	https://www.linkedin.com/company/errin	ERRIN_Network	https://twitter.com/ERRINNetwork	N/A	N/A	https://errin.eu/
SoScience	https://www.linkedin.com/company/soscience	SoScienceTweet	https://twitter.com/SoScienceTweet	https://www.facebook.com/SoScience	N/A	www.soscience.org
Stickydot	https://www.linkedin.com/company/stickydot	stickydoteu	https://twitter.com/stickydoteu	https://www.facebook.com/stickydoteu	N/A	https://stickydot.eu/
Uni Gustave Eiffel	https://www.linkedin.com/school/universit%C3%A9-gustave-eiffel/	UGustaveEiffel	https://twitter.com/UGustaveEiffel	https://www.facebook.com/UniversiteGustaveEiffel/	https://www.instagram.com/universitegustaveeiffel/	https://www.univ-gustave-eiffel.fr/
Fondazione Gianni Bassetti (FGB)	https://www.linkedin.com/company/fondazionebassetti/	FGBassetti	https://twitter.com/FGBassetti	https://www.facebook.com/groups/148256638400/	N/A	https://www.fondazionebassetti.org/en/

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5.1 Hashtags

Official hashtags for MOSAIC and initiatives related to the project can be used on both Twitter and LinkedIn. They are:

- #MOSAICeu
- #MissionCities – this is the hashtag used for the discussions about the Horizon Europe Mission on Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities
- #RRI
- #OpenInnovation

**# HASHTAGS
WHAT NOT TO DO**

<u>ONE</u> Don't use spaces or punctuation in your hashtags	<u>TWO</u> Don't use the @ symbol in a hashtag	<u>THREE</u> Don't go overboard with too many hashtags
<u>FOUR</u> Make sure your hashtags stay relevant to the content of your post	<u>FIVE</u> Don't string too many words together in a hashtag	<u>SIX</u> Use trending hashtags specific to your sector

Figure 13 - How to use #

5.2 Twitter

5.2.1 Best practice

The best time to post on Twitter is on weekdays between 09:00 and 13:00, though consistent engagement continues until 16:00. In 2021, a single tweet has a life span of around 15-20 minutes and so it is important that MOSAIC partners target tweets to the correct audience, using visual aids to ensure the optimal reach of every tweet. One of the best uses of Twitter is to follow live events in real time and so it will be a vital tool for events, both online and in person, organised or attended by the MOSAIC project.

Coordinated communications for MOSAIC partners will include visual material for Twitter, this may be images or animated images in the form of gifs.

Consistent posting is key and tweets or retweets from the MOSAIC Twitter should be shared every day. To facilitate this, Tweet scheduling tools such as Hootsuite, or Twitter's built-in scheduling function, may be used.

5.2.2 Threads

Twitter threads are a series of tweets related to each other and can generate higher engagement as they allow tweets to resurface on users' feeds. They should be used for developing subjects or live-tweeting an event. For example, if a MOSAIC tweet about the upcoming MOSAIC Toolkit performed well, replying to the tweet sometime later with a link to the toolkit once published would create a thread and engage the previous tweet's audience. Threads are also useful for storytelling and can be used to share stories from the ground of MOSAIC's pilot and mirror ecosystems.

5.2.3 Visual content

With the exception of threads, tweets should always contain an image, gif or video as it improves the likelihood of users finding and engaging with a tweet. It also allows other organisations and partners to be tagged without using up the limited character count.

5.2.4 Handles, tagging & hashtags

MOSAIC will be active on Twitter with the handle [@MOSAIC_EU](https://twitter.com/MOSAIC_EU). Project partners should try to tag this either in the tweet itself (ideally embedded in the text) or tag the MOSAIC profile in any visual material attached to a tweet. This is to ensure the growth of the MOSAIC Twitter account and the project's overall reach. It is also encouraged to tag partners, as listed in the table above, and other organisations and networks, especially for important announcements. Tweets should not be overloaded with tags and hashtags; embedding a maximum of two or three into the tweet's text is a better approach. For example:

Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

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5.2.5 Tweets and links

Tweets are limited to 240 characters. Text language should not be used to condense content into a tweet. It is advisable to use links in your tweet, but they should be shortened to save characters. Links can be shortened using the link shortening tool bit.ly. Partners are also encouraged to engage with MOSAIC's Twitter account by liking and retweeting (with or without comment) MOSAIC's tweets.

5.2.6 Monitoring & KPIs

As stipulated in the project application, the MOSAIC Twitter account has several key performance indicators (KPIs) to reach:

KPI	M18	M36
Followers on Twitter	100	350
Mentions on Twitter	40	100
Engagement rate	54	198

To ensure these KPIs are reached on time and to be able to monitor the success of the MOSAIC Twitter account, Twitter analytics and Google Analytics for the MOSAIC website will be used to monitor:

- Followers
- Mentions
- Likes
- Retweets without comment
- Link clicks
- Engagement rate
- Social media referral (to MOSAIC website)

Key statistics will be gathered monthly by ERRIN and added to an Excel sheet, which will be monitored closely in order to detect any trends as well as follow the reach of and engagement around the content posted on the MOSAIC Twitter account. This will enable ERRIN and the PCT to correct and update the project's communication efforts on Twitter if necessary.

5.2.7 Visual identity

The below graphics are the MOSAIC project's Twitter page banner and profile picture, designed for the specification of Twitter.

Figure 14 MOSAIC Twitter banner

Figure 15 MOSAIC Twitter profile picture

5.3 LinkedIn

5.3.1 Best practices

The LinkedIn page will aim to create a community around the concept of missions and co-creation and MOSAIC, making use of the personal/professional engagement fostered on the platform. The best time to post on LinkedIn is weekdays between 10:00 and 12:00. LinkedIn posts have a longer lifespan than tweets, around 48 hours. To perform well on LinkedIn, MOSAIC must use tagging strategically and engage directly with interested parties.

Consistent posting is key, and original or shared posts on the MOSAIC LinkedIn page should be published several times a week. To facilitate this, a post scheduling tool such as Hootsuite may be used.

5.3.2 Handles, tagging and 'employees'

MOSAIC's company page on LinkedIn is active at <https://www.linkedin.com/company/MOSAIC-eu>. LinkedIn is designed for individual users to engage with content on the platform, and so MOSAIC partners will be encouraged to mark their involvement in MOSAIC by adding it to their work experience section on LinkedIn. This will make the most of the networking tools within LinkedIn and notify partners of other 'employee activity' within the project. However, only ERRIN will be able to post on the LinkedIn public page. MOSAIC can be tagged on LinkedIn via @MOSAIC.

5.3.3 Content & links

Like Twitter, visual material is essential to LinkedIn posts' reach, so partners will regularly be provided with visuals to use with MOSAIC LinkedIn content. LinkedIn is also suited to longer-form text and so previews from articles from the MOSAIC website can be shared and linked to the article. Links can be shortened using the link shortening tool bit.ly.

5.3.4 LinkedIn Group

LinkedIn groups occupy a public-private space for professionals to exchange experiences and insights on a shared topic. As the project proceeds, MOSAIC will consider having its own group or making use of a pre-existing group, that will be open to project partners and other individuals interested in RRI, co-creation and the cities mission. Such a group may provide an opportunity for external actors to learn more about and engage with the project and serve as a means to source and share other content on the MOSAIC public page.

5.3.5 Monitoring & KPIs

As stipulated in the project application, the MOSAIC LinkedIn activities will have several key performance indicators (KPIs) to reach:

KPI	M18	M36
Engagement rate	0.7%	1.2%
Group growth	150	500
Page reach (last 10 publications impressions)	500	2000

To ensure these KPIs are reached on time and to be able to monitor the success of the MOSAIC LinkedIn page, LinkedIn analytics and Google Analytics for the MOSAIC website will be used to monitor:

- Reactions
- Comments
- Shares
- Clicks
- Followers
- Engagement rate
- Social media referral (to MOSAIC website)

Key statistics will be gathered monthly by ERRIN and added to an Excel sheet, which will be monitored closely in order to detect any trends as well as follow the reach of and engagement around the content posted on the MOSAIC LinkedIn account. This will enable ERRIN and the PCT to correct and update the project's communication efforts on LinkedIn if necessary.

5.3.6 Visual identity

The below graphics are the MOSAIC project's LinkedIn page banner and profile picture, designed for the specification of the page.

Figure 16 MOSAIC LinkedIn page banner

Figure 17 MOSAIC LinkedIn page profile picture

5.4 Social Media at Events

Social media use is vital at events, both internally and externally. Firstly, it will help promote the event through greater traffic and online interaction, especially important for events that MOSAIC hosts. Interacting with others at the event will also raise MOSAIC's social media profile, through virtual networking, leading to a greater audience. It is also a useful means of sharing MOSAIC's activities with collaborators, highlighting attendance at each event, and bringing updates directly from the speakers.

The main tool used should be Twitter. This allows for quick, regular updates as opposed to LinkedIn, which is not suited for mass posting. As discussed in the best practices above, threads of tweets can be used gather the live-tweeting of an event. Twitter also enables interaction with other attendees and speakers.

Photographs can be uploaded to Twitter, accompanied by a caption or description. After the event this will then provide a selection of photos for further reporting.

The following table can be used to help prepare for events. By completing the table ahead of time, it will make finding participants easier. Tweeting accounts directly can create engagement and attention for MOSAIC, as well as lending authenticity to tweets. Tracking an event hashtags is important when hosting an event as you can follow all the tweets related to the event and interact with the select content through retweeting or replying directly.

Name	Area/Session	Title and role in event	Twitter handle (include @)	Organisation's Twitter handle (include @)

7. Newsletter

MOSAIC will produce **six** newsletters throughout the lifetime of the project. The newsletter will be designed and sent on MailChimp, where registrants data will be managed in accordance with GDPR guidance. Partners and all stakeholders will be invited to sign up to the newsletter before the first issue is sent. It will also be possible to sign up to the newsletter on the homepage of the MOSAIC website, where previous issues of the newsletter will be gathered. Partners will be encouraged to share the newsletter on their communication channels to increase its potential reach.

7.1. KPIs & Monitoring

As stipulated in the project application, the MOSAIC Newsletter has a key performance indicators (KPI) to reach:

KPI	M18	M36
Total number of readers of MOSAIC's newsletter	100	300

In order to ensure this KPI is reached on time and to be able to monitor the success of the MOSAIC of the MOSAIC newsletter, MailChimp's newsletter reports will be monitored for:

- Registered
- Recipients
- Successful deliveries
- Total opens
- Forwards
- Opened
- Clicked
- Bounced
- Unsubscribed
- Open rate
- Click rate
- URL clicks.

Key statistics will be gathered after the publication of a new newsletter by ERRIN and added to an Excel sheet, which will be monitored regularly in order to detect any significant changes in the reach and engagement for the MOSAIC newsletters. This will enable ERRIN and the PCT to potentially change the content of the newsletters, the design of them, or any other aspects.

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7.2. Timeline

During the first six months of the project, the MOSAIC mailing list will be built on MailChimp. Individuals interested in the project will be encouraged to sign up to the newsletter on the MOSAIC website, on social media, at events and by word-of-mouth. The first issue will then be sent in M6, and subsequent issues will be sent every six months after that.

Project Month	Newsletter issue
6	1
12	2
18	3
24	4
30	5
36	6

See section **Error! Reference source not found.0 - Error! Reference source not found.** for more information on the overall timeline of the CDE activities.

8. Visual guidelines

8.1. Colours

The visual identity of the MOSAIC project has been developed to ensure the project and its outputs are easily recognisable. The key colours that should be used in the creation of visual material for the MOSAIC project are as follows:

- Primary colour: #BC204B
- Secondary colour: #E1523E
- Complementary colours (to be used less often):
 - #C62D48
 - CF3945
 - D84642

The colours are demonstrated below.

PANTONE 7636 c
RGB 188 32 75
HEX/HTML BC204B
CMYK 0 100 44 14

PANTONE 7625 c
RGB 225 82 62
HEX/HTML E1523E
CMYK 0 80 78 0

8.2. Branding Guidelines

The full branding guidelines are integrated into this document – double click on the image below to open the PDF document.

Figure 18 - Branding Guidelines

8.3. Icons

A set of icons have been identified to illustrate various facets of the MOSAIC project. Their repeated use will become synonymous for the tools and subjects they represent. These symbols will be used on the MOSAIC website as well as on promotional material including infographics and social media visuals. The icons identified so far are presented in the table below, though the list is not exhaustive and may change throughout the duration of the project.

Subject, idea or tool within MOSAIC	Symbol(s)
Co-creation	
Mission	

Industry	
Policymakers	
Citizens	
Ecosystem	
Academia	
Research & innovation	
Climate neutral & smart cities	

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9. Exploitation

As previously stated, exploitation is the “utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.”³

The MOSAIC project will look to effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society.

ERRIN will run an internal workshop with the project partners in M5 of the project to ascertain which project results will have exploitable value. In addition to the partners' external efforts, all Key Exploitable Results (KERs) will be uploaded to the Horizon Results Platform during the project lifetime.

9.1. Key Exploitable Results (KERs) PLAN

This table will be completed by Work Package leaders and then shared with project partners.

WP Number	Deliverable Number and Title ⁴	Key exploitable Result (-s) ⁵	Type ⁶	Short Description ⁷	Target Group ⁸	Foreseen KPIs ⁹	Potential impact ¹⁰

³ (Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)

⁴ Deliverable number (see Grant Agreement – DoA) - KER can be also merged from several deliverables.

⁵ It can be also only a part of a deliverable (e.g. methodology, service, product, etc.)

⁶ Report, Service, Product, Data set (anonymised)

⁷ Main exploitable characteristics of the identified KER

⁸ Potential Users during or after project implementation

⁹ E.g. number of users, etc.

¹⁰ To identify impacts, see the impact section in the Grant Agreement – DoA – Section 2.1.

10.Overall Timeline

KEY COMMUNICATION TASKS TIMELINE												
APRIL	MAY	JUNE	JULY	AUGUST	SEPTEMBER	OCTOBER	NOVEMBER	DECEMBER	JANUARY	FEBRUARY	MARCH	APRIL
		NEWSLETTER #1						NEWSLETTER #2				
WP5 COMMS MEETING & MAPPING OF WP EVENTS	EXPLOITATION MEETING	MISSION LAUNCH					PROMOTION: TAXONOMY OF MISSION CONTEXTS					
LAUNCH OF THE MOSAIC WEBSITE							PROMOTION: EXPERIENCES OF CO-CREATION FROM SWAFS	UPDATE OF THE CDE STRATEGY	PROMOTION: MISSION CONTEXT CROSS CHARTING REPORT			
CREATION OF PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL	CREATION OF PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL	CREATION OF PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL	CREATION OF PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL	CREATION OF PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL	CREATION OF PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL	CREATION OF PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL	STORIES FROM THE MIRROR ECOSYSTEMS	STORIES FROM THE MIRROR ECOSYSTEMS	STORIES FROM THE MIRROR ECOSYSTEMS	STORIES FROM THE MIRROR ECOSYSTEMS	STORIES FROM THE MIRROR ECOSYSTEMS	STORIES FROM THE MIRROR ECOSYSTEMS
	CATCH UP WITH THE PCT & CCPS		CATCH UP WITH THE PCT & CCPS		CATCH UP WITH THE PCT & CCPS		CATCH UP WITH THE PCT & CCPS		CATCH UP WITH THE PCT & CCPS		CATCH UP WITH THE PCT & CCPS	
						STORIES FROM THE PILOTS' CO-DESIGN PROCESSES	STORIES FROM THE PILOTS' CO-DESIGN PROCESSES	STORIES FROM THE PILOTS' CO-DESIGN PROCESSES	STORIES FROM THE PILOTS' CO-DESIGN PROCESSES	STORIES FROM THE PILOTS' CO-DESIGN PROCESSES	STORIES FROM THE PILOTS' CO-DESIGN PROCESSES	

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11. Annexe

This section of the document will collect all of the guides, mappings and monitoring that will be collected during the course of the project. The first update of this section will come in M12.

11.1. Branding Guidelines

11.2. Communication & Dissemination Guide

Expected in month 4.

11.3. Social Media Guide

Expected in month 4.

11.4. Image Bank

Expected in month 4 – already available on the Next Cloud.

11.5. Partner Mapping

Expected in Month 5 after the workshop in month 4.

11.6. Work Package Mapping

Expected in Month 5 after the workshop in month 4.

